

InterAgency Institute
BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

THE USE OF CYBERSPACE AND INTERAGENCY ACTION IN THE PREVENTION-ELIMINATION OF HUMAN TRAFFICKING

Luzia Costa Becker
Marta Beatriz Martins da Costa

December 20th, 2023.

Policy Statement

In the context of implementing the UN's 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, SDGs 5, 8, and 6 directly reference eliminating human trafficking. The fight against organized crime to exploit people as a lucrative commodity requires a focus on diverse initiatives to protect human beings who are suffering from exploitation. Considering that the trafficking and the subjugation of human beings for commercial purposes – such as forced labor, sexual exploitation, and debt bondage, among other forms of abuse – has increased with the use of new technologies, this paper argues that containing this advance requires a type of interagency concertation in building a network to protect people in situations of vulnerability at the local and global levels.

Background

According to the Palermo Protocol (UN: 2000), conceived within the framework of the United Nations, trafficking in persons is defined as the recruitment, transportation, transfer, harboring, or receipt of persons through the threat or use of force or other forms of coercion, of abduction, of fraud, of deception, of the abuse of power or a position of vulnerability or the giving or receiving of payments or benefits to achieve the consent of a person having control over another person, for exploitation. Exploitation shall include, as a minimum, the exploitation of the prostitution of others or other forms of sexual exploitation, forced labor or services, slavery or practices similar to slavery, servitude, or the removal of organs [1]. According to the United Nations (2014), inequalities within and between countries, increasingly restrictive immigration policies, and the growing demand for cheap labor are the underlying causes of this scenario. Poverty, violence, and discrimination make individuals vulnerable to trafficking.

Human trafficking is considered in three of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals – SDGs, a global action plan to eliminate extreme poverty and hunger, provide lifelong quality education for all, protect the planet, and promote peaceful and inclusive societies by 2030 (UN: 2015). In SDG 5 – gender equality – target 5.2 is to eliminate all forms of violence against all women and girls in the public and private spheres, including trafficking and sexual and other exploitation. In SDG 8 – decent work and

economic growth – target 8.7 is to take immediate and effective measures to eradicate forced labor, end modern slavery and human trafficking, and ensure the prohibition and elimination of the worst forms of child labor, including recruitment and use of child soldiers, and by 2025 end child labor in all its forms. In SDG 16 – peace, justice, and strong institutions – target 16.2 is to end abuse, exploitation, trafficking, and all forms of violence and torture against children.

In the context of the European Commission's 2020 work program, a new comprehensive approach to trafficking in human beings has been adopted among its main actions aimed at combating organized crime. The Strategy to Combat Trafficking in Human Beings (2021-2025) focuses on preventing crime, bringing traffickers to justice, and protecting and empowering victims. It builds on the EU's existing comprehensive legal and policy framework to combat trafficking in human beings, rooted in the Anti-Trafficking Directive. The Commission will support Member States in implementing Directive 2011/36/EU on preventing and combating trafficking in human beings and, if necessary, propose revisions to ensure that it is fit for purpose (European Parliament: 2021).

Findings

Because it is a recurring phenomenon in almost every country in the world, human trafficking represents one of the illicit industries with the most significant development and growth worldwide (Gutierrez et al., 2020), as it consists of a highly profitable trade generating around 32 million dollars annually, surpassing the world's primary illicit industries such as drug and arms trafficking (Smith et al., 2014).

The high profitability of the illicit business is because human beings are one of the only "commodities" that can be sold repeatedly, making it one of the most lucrative ventures in the world, given that there are more than 20 million victims of human trafficking worldwide (European Parliament, 2016), with an increase of around 2 million victims every year (Nogueira & Abreu, 2023). Sexual exploitation is the most common form of trafficking, comprising 79% of the trade (UNODC, 2009).

This sad but favorable scenario for criminals has been optimized with the use of technology applied to the cooptation of people through social networks. According to

Europol, cybercrime based on human trafficking is a growing phenomenon whose dynamic and distinct characteristics from other exploitation mechanisms allow easy access through the internet to contact victims, through the anonymity that the technological space confers and the difficulties presented by the authorities in identifying and locating traffickers (Europol, 2021).

In addition to this issue, the introduction of communication technologies has brought about a significant paradigm shift not only in terms of the actions of the trafficker but also in terms of the characteristics of the victims. The ease of access to new technologies has brought a new trend of an increase in victims with higher education qualifications and from higher social strata, attracted by false job vacancies advertised online (Dixon, 2013) and whose ease of transportation, infrastructure, and other accommodation benefits the process of human trafficking for exploitation through social networks.

The use of digital platforms for human trafficking purposes has facilitated the development and growth of the phenomenon: the process of identifying victims and contacting them has become faster and more accessible, the logistics of transferring money have been made easier, as has coordination between groups and the guarantee of anonymity (Council of Europe, 2022). In this way, human trafficking has undergone a paradigm shift that has made victims even more vulnerable. Communication is now possible from different geographical points between other countries or continents. While the forms of abuse were previously strictly physical, today, they encompass the sale and exposure of material online (Landron, 2021), such as images, videos, and virtual sex, among other crimes.

New market opportunities have led to the emergence of international trafficking networks, in which vulnerable groups and their socio-economic situation increase their exposure to trafficking and exploitation (Wheaton et al., 2010). In this way, cyberspace, as the primary vehicle for communication, has become a risk mainly for regions of extreme poverty, marked by inequalities and conflicts of an economic, political, religious, or social nature, which have become highly exposed to global demands for human exploitation (Martellozzo & Jane, 2017).

Through the darkest layers of the internet – such as network servers inaccessible through conventional search engines, the "Deep Web" and "Dark Web" phenomena –

grooming victims, who are captured and sold for exploitation via the internet, is the new bet of transnational criminals, as it is a criminal engineering that is difficult for states to access. In cyberspace, the sale of erotic photos and videos in which victims are abused on camera is practiced, among other crimes, and the confidentiality of transactions, business deals, and transfers of value are guaranteed for the proper functioning of criminal activity (Nazemi, 2011).

Gaps in the financial, technological, and educational structure, especially in the poorest countries, make it challenging to create effective mechanisms to combat human trafficking on the internet, where traffickers seek to recruit through fraudulent job advertisements, mainly with a view to sexual and labor exploitation (Graham, 2023). The online recruitment of victims, the use of sexually exploitative material, live streaming, and the use of child sexual abuse material have increased significantly (Observer, 2019). More than 500,000 images and videos of sexual abuse of minors under the age of 10 have been recorded with cell phones and sold on digital platforms by the victims' parents to make a profit (Prudente, 2020).

Portugal is recorded as a country of origin, transit, and destination for trafficking in human beings. According to the OTSH, the majority of trafficked victims - around 70% - are men for labor exploitation, mainly in the agricultural, construction, domestic service and cleaning, restaurant, and hotel sectors (European Commission, 2023). However, trafficking for sexual exploitation and children for theft also takes place, albeit in minimal numbers (OSTH, 2021).

The legal treatment of trafficking in human beings in Portugal is still highly inadequate (US Department of State, 2022), although it has been punished as a crime since the first Portuguese penal code. The legal gaps in the country's legislation have been worked on but are still visible. It was only in 2008 that Portugal made a profound change to what it considered to be the crime of human trafficking. Before, the phenomenon was conceived only from the point of view of an attack on sexual freedom and self-determination, and only later was it integrated as a crime against personal liberty (Coso, 2018).

Despite the importance of this change, the Portuguese system is still not fully capable of dealing with the actual dimension of human trafficking (US Department of State, 2022). There is a significant lack of knowledge about its proper dimension, not only

because of technological gaps and investment in research, awareness-raising, legal development, debate, and interstate and interagency cooperation (Matos et al., 2019). Weak legislation also means a feeble fight against human trafficking. Between 2007 and 2015, an analysis of 30 criminal cases related to human trafficking in Portugal revealed that 71% were closed, and only 2% resulted in the conviction of the traffickers (Matos et al., 2019). The fight against human trafficking entered the Portuguese public agenda with the signing of the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime in 2000 and with the signing of the Council of Europe Convention on Action against Trafficking in Human Beings. It can be said that the driving force behind the fight against human trafficking was governmental organizations, such as the Commission for Citizenship and Gender Equality – CIG (Clemente, 2019).

On the other hand, the Portuguese approach to combating human trafficking ends up limiting the activity of non-governmental organizations because it is tied to a security perspective with the main focus on national security and the punishment of traffickers, in a logic of subordination of the trafficked victim to the prosecution of the crime of trafficking. For this reason, the fight against human trafficking in Portugal has been developed around repressive actions against the victims themselves, such as migration control, increased border control, deportation, and restrictive migration policies, among other practices that led to the conception of human trafficking as a migratory problem (Clemente, 2022).

The country's conception of the nature of human trafficking results in the dilapidation of the interests of trafficked persons since it subordinates the victim to the pursuit of the trafficker, restricting the victim's rights to participate in investigations in collaboration with national authorities under penalty of deportation and intimidating threats.

Recommendations

Within the European Union, member states are recommended to consider the European Commission's strategy for the eradication of human trafficking, which proposes a series of actions around five main axes:

- (i) Prevention, protection, and prosecution, in which we highlight ensuring adequate funding to combat trafficking inside and outside the EU.
- (ii) Reducing the demand that fosters trafficking includes organizing a prevention campaign conducted jointly with member states and civil society organizations, targeting high-risk sectors and environments.
- (iii) Breaking the criminal model to prevent the exploitation of victims. This includes improving registration and data collection to ensure reliable and comparable information for tailored policies and promoting dialogue and the exchange of best practices with the support of EU agencies with the private sector and digital industries.
- (iv) Protect, support, and empower victims, including ensuring funding for non-governmental organizations in non-EU partner countries to support victims' psychosocial needs; developing close cooperation with the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions to improve the impact of anti-trafficking actions with social and economic partners and at local and regional level; strengthen partnerships with non-EU countries to ensure that victims' rights are guaranteed during all stages of the return process and that they receive specific and personalized assistance and protection upon return, including particular safeguards for children.

In the specific case of Portugal, among others, it is suggested to:

- (i) Enact a legal provision on the non-punishment of victims to ensure that victims of trafficking are not inappropriately penalized for illegal acts that traffickers force them to commit, including administrative and immigration-related infractions.
- (ii) Enable victims' identification and formal referral by entities other than the police, including civil society, social workers, and health professionals.
- (iii) Increase the involvement of survivors, including by establishing accessible mechanisms to receive and compensate survivor input in developing policies, programs, and training (US Department of State, 2022).

Conclusions

Trafficking in human beings is "an attack on humanity, embodied in an unspeakable aggression against human rights, because it exploits the person, limits their freedom, despises their honor, affronts their dignity, threatens and takes their life" (Barros: 2013, p. 16). This complex, transnational, low-risk, high-profit criminal activity, which manifests itself in different ways in different parts of the world, victimizing millions of people around the world in a barbaric and profound way, must be globally researched, analyzed, identified, and combated. To this end, we need to think about a type of inter-agency concertation, in other words, an international network for acting and monitoring the impact of the various actions to prevent and eradicate human trafficking through studies focusing on the indicators of SDGs 5, 8 and 16 related to the issue.

References

Gutierrez, Emma Carolina Arguelles; García, Montserrat Cabrera; Báez, Luis Alfonso Elizalde (2020). Addressing the increase in Human Trafficking viewed worldwide. Accessed on 20/Oct/2023. Available in [578-5d9d4525bce4557fcf30ff35 EN OHCHR-A.pdf \(iniciativa2025alc.org\)](#).

Barros, Rinaldo Aparecido. Apresentação. In Brazil. Secretaria Nacional de Justiça. Tráfico de pessoas: uma abordagem para os direitos humanos / Secretaria Nacional de Justiça, Departamento de Justiça, Classificação, Títulos e Qualificação; organização de Fernanda Alves dos Anjos... [et al.]. – 1. ed. Brasília: Ministério da Justiça, 2013.

Clemente, Mara (2019). O tráfico sexual (já não é sexy? Atores, definições do problema e políticas no campo português de combate ao tráfico. *Gazeta de Antropologia*, n. 35,1. Accessed on 20/Nov/2023. Available in <http://www.gazeta-antropologia.es/?p=5104>

Clemente, Mara (2022). A construção do campo de combate ao tráfico de pessoas em Portugal: O papel das organizações não-governamentais. Accessed on 20/Nov/2023. Available in https://www.researchgate.net/publication/362348259_A_construcao_do_campo_de_combate_ao_trafico_de_pessoas_em_Portugal_O_papel_das_organizacaoes_nao-governamentais

Coso, Emiliano García (2018). Las iniciativas multinivel para combatir la trata de seres humanos y el crimen organizado transnacional: la protección de las víctimas por el TEDH. *Revista del Ministerio de Empleo y Seguridad Social: Revista del Ministerio de Trabajo, Migraciones y Seguridad Social*, (135), 19-50. 55

Council of Europe (2022). *Online and technology-facilitated the trafficking of human beings. Summary and Recommendations*. Accessed on 23/Nov/2023. Available in: [1680a5e10c \(coe.int\)](#)

DIXON, Herbert B. Júnior (2013). Human trafficking and the internet (and other technologies, too). *The Judges' Journal*, Volume 52, Number 1, Winter 2013. Accessed on 23/Nov/2023. Available in https://www.americanbar.org/content/dam/aba/publications/judges_journal/vol52no1-jj2013-tech.pdf

European commission (2023). General information: situation on trafficking in human beings. Accessed on 20/Nov/2023. Available in https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/internal-security/organised-crime-and-human-trafficking/together-against-trafficking-human-beings/eu-countries/portugal_en

European Parliament (2021). Strategy towards the eradication of trafficking in human beings. In "Promoting our European Way of Life," Accessed on 7/dec/2023. Available in <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/theme-promoting-our-european-way-of-life/file-eradication-of-trafficking-in-human-beings>

Europol (2021). Europol Programming Document 2022–2024. Accessed on 30/Nov/2023. Available in: https://www.europol.europa.eu/cms/sites/default/files/documents/the_challenges_of_countersing_human_trafficking_in_the_digital_era.pdf

Graham, Jamie Kay (2023). The Dark Web and Human Trafficking. Accessed on 20/Nov/2023. Available in digitalcommons.liberty.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=5274&context=doctoral

Landron, Gabriela (2021). Human Trafficking and Its Evolution into Cyberspace: How Has Technology Transformed Human Trafficking Over Time?. Honors Undergraduate Theses. Accessed on 23/Nov/2023. Available in <https://stars.library.ucf.edu/honorstheses/1062/>

Matos, Marlene; Gonçalves, Mariana; Maia, Ângela. (2019). Understanding the criminal justice process in human trafficking cases in Portugal: factors associated with successful prosecutions. *Crime, law, and social change*, 72, 501-525.

Martellozzo, Elena & Jane, Emma A. (2017). *Cybercrime and its victims*. Taylor & Francis. Published March 5, 2019 by Routledge.

Nações Unidas Brasil (2021). Tráfico de pessoas abuse da tecnologia online para fazer mais vítimas. Accessed on 20/nov/2023 Available in: [Tráfico de pessoas abuse da tecnologia online para fazer mais vítimas | As Nações Unidas no Brasil](#)

Nazemi, Nazafarin. (2011). Role of Internet in Human Trafficking. *Indian Journal of Social Development*, 11(2), 517–540. Accessed on 23/Nov/2023. Available in https://www.researchgate.net/publication/259383161_Role_of_Internet_in_Human_Trafficking

Nogueira, Lhayanna De Cássia Monteiro; Abreu, Ivy de Souza (2023). The Profitability of Human Trafficking and Its "Modus Operandi Online." Accessed on 22/Nov/2023. Available in <https://multivix.edu.br/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/a-rentabilidade-do-traffic-humano-e-o-seu-modus-operandi-on-line.pdf>

Observador (2019). Em 2018, foram detectados 45 milhões de vídeos e fotografias de crianças sexualmente abusadas na internet. Accessed on 15/nov/2023. Available in <https://observador.pt/2019/09/29/em-2018-foram-detetados-45-milhoes-de-videos-e-fotografias-de-criancas-sexualmente-abusadas-na-internet/>

ONU (2000). Protocolo Adicional à Convenção das Nações Unidas Contra o Crime Organizado Transnacional Relativo à Prevenção, Repressão e Punição do Tráfico de Pessoas, em Especial Mulheres e Crianças. Accessed on 5/dec/2023. Available <https://www.mdm.org.pt/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/Protocolo-de-Palermo.pdf>

Parlamento Europeu. Tráfico De Seres Humanos: mais de 20 milhões de vítimas no mundo (2016). Accessed on 3/dec/2023. Available in <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/pt/headlines/world/20161014ST047261/traffic-de-seres-humanos-mais-de-20-milhoes-de-vitimas-no-mundo>

Prudente, Amanda Juncal. (2020) O Impacto da Deep Web no Tráfico Humano: Análise a partir da responsabilidade do Estado.. Dissertação (Mestrado). Programa de Pós-Graduação em Ciência Jurídica. UENP. Accessed on 10/Nov/2023. Available in <https://uenp.edu.br/pos-direito-teses-dissertacoes-defendidas/direito-dissertacoes/16224-amanda-juncal-prudente/file>

Osth (2021). Tráfico de Seres Humanos. Relatório sobre 2020. Accessed on 20/Nov/2023. Available in <https://www.otsh.mai.gov.pt/wp-content/uploads/Observatorio-Trafico-Seres-Humanos-Relatorio-Anual-Estatistico-Trafico-de-Seres-Humanos-2020.pdf>

Siqueira, Priscila (2013). Tráfico de pessoas: comércio infamante num mundo globalizado. In Brasil. Secretaria Nacional de Justiça. Tráfico de pessoas: uma abordagem para os direitos humanos/Secretaria Nacional de Justiça, Departamento de Justiça, Classificação, Títulos e Qualificação; organização de Fernanda Alves dos Anjos [et al.]. – 1.ed. Brasília: Ministério da Justiça.

Smith, Katherine T.; Russel, Hanna; Smith, Murphy (2014). Human trafficking: a global multi-billion dollar criminal industry. *International Journal of Public Law and Policy*, 4(3), 293–308. Accessed on 3/dec/2023. Available in https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2316169

Unodc (2009). Global Report on Trafficking in Persons. Accessed on 20/Nov/2023. Available in https://www.unodc.org/documents/Global_Report_on_TIP.pdf

United Nations. The Crime: Defining Human Trafficking. Accessed 3/dec/2023. Available in <https://www.unodc.org/unodc/en/human-trafficking/crime.html>

US Department of State (2022). Trafficking in Persons Report: Portugal. Accessed on 3/dec/2023. Available in <https://www.state.gov/reports/2022-trafficking-in-persons-report/portugal/>

[1] On 15/11/2000, the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA) adopted the Protocol to Prevent, Suppress, and Punish Trafficking in Persons, Especially Women and Children, known as the Palermo Protocol, supplementing the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime. This Convention aims to promote cooperation in order to tackle this crime more effectively, establishing a global language and legislation that defines what human trafficking is (SIQUEIRA: 2013, p 24).

Luzia Costa Becker (InterAgency Institute): PhD in Political Science at IUPERJ (IESP). Postdoctoral fellow at HU Berlin, Germany (2015) and UFF Niteroi, Brazil (2017).

Marta Beatriz Martins da Costa (InterAgency Institute): Master Candidate in Strategy at ISCSP, University of Lisbon. Bachelor´s degree in Political Science and International Relations from Lusófona University Lisbon.

InterAgency Institute

<https://interagency.institute/>
contact@interagency.institute

Editor-in-chief: Larlecianne Piccolli
